

Ultra-Wideband Temperature Dependent Dielectric Spectroscopy of Blood in the Microwave Frequency Range

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Abstract—The knowledge of temperature dependent dielectric properties of biological tissue in the microwave frequency range is crucial for medical applications such as microwave temperature monitoring during oncological treatments. This paper deals with temperature dependent dielectric spectroscopy of blood by means of ultra-wideband sensing. We present the results of relative permittivity and conductivity of blood without agents and blood with heparin in the frequency range of 0.5 GHz up to 7 GHz and in the temperature range between 30 °C and 50 °C. The measurements show that the addition of heparin does not affect the dielectric properties in the considered frequency and temperature range. Furthermore, the measurements are compatible with the few data reported in the literature.

Index Terms—dielectric spectroscopy, temperature dependent properties of blood, M-sequence, open-ended coaxial probe, UWB

I. INTRODUCTION

Thermotherapy (e.g. hyperthermia) is being used to support cancer treatments (e.g. chemotherapy and radiotherapy). Hyperthermia is typically induced by radio frequencies, ultrasound or microwaves and employs a temperature range between 41 °C and 45 °C [1]. Temperatures above 45 °C result in cell destruction. Therefore, it is necessary to monitor the temperature during the thermal treatment continuously. In general, temperature probes (e.g. fiber optic catheters) measure the temperature in the region of interest, whereby this procedure is invasive and the spatial resolution is limited to one single point per probe. Microwave temperature monitoring might be a promising alternative due to the non-invasive measurement procedure and a higher spatial resolution. The approach is based on the temperature dependent interaction of an electromagnetic wave with biological tissue [2]–[4]. Selective heating of a target area (e.g. cancerous tissue) results in a change of its dielectric properties and consequently in a changing scattering behavior of the electromagnetic wave. These differences can be measured by means of ultra-wideband (UWB) radar technology as shown in initial phantom studies [4], [5]. To evaluate the UWB differential signal corresponding to the temperature change within the tissue, it is essential to know the temperature dependent dielectric properties in the microwave frequency range.

A variety of studies have reported on the dielectric properties of different tissues, but most of them only consider the complex permittivity at a constant temperature [6], [7]. To our knowledge the temperature dependency of dielectric properties over a wide frequency range has only been reported in a few studies such as animal liver in the frequency range between 0.5 GHz and 20 GHz by Lazebnik et al. [8], human as well as animal blood in the frequency range up to 1 GHz by Jaspard and Nadi [9] and human blood in the frequency range between 0.4 GHz and 20 GHz by Salahuddin et al [10]. Further studies investigated the temperature dependency only at discrete frequencies. A summary of temperature dependent dielectric properties of tissue can be found in Rossmann and Haemmerich [11].

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the temperature dependent relative permittivity and effective conductivity of porcine blood in a frequency range of 0.5 GHz up to 7 GHz and a temperature range between 30 °C and 50 °C in steps of 1 °C.

Fig. 1: Measurement setup for UWB spectroscopy of blood using an UWB M-sequence NWA connected to the coaxial probe (performance probe, Keysight Technologies). A temperature probe connected to the high precision thermometer (GMH 3750, GHM Messtechnik GmbH) records the temperature. Both, UWB radar signals and temperature are stored by a custom developed software in parallel.

Fig. 2: Mean relative permittivity ϵ' and mean effective conductivity σ of blood without heparin (a,c) and blood with heparin (b,d) as a function of frequency at different temperatures.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Measurement setup

The dielectric spectroscopy was performed using a coaxial probe (N1501A performance probe, Keysight Technologies, Santa Clara, CA). The probe was connected to an M-sequence network analyzer developed at Technische Universität Ilmenau [13]. Fig. 1 shows the UWB measurement setup for the temperature dependent dielectric spectroscopy of blood. The setup is mostly identical with the one presented in [14]. In addition, we used a magnetic stirrer to avoid sedimentation of the cellular components during the measurement.

B. Blood samples

In this study we used samples of fresh blood obtained from a local slaughter house. First, we measured three samples of fresh blood from different pigs without any additional agents. These measurements started within two hours after blood collection. Furthermore, we investigated three samples of fresh blood with heparin. The samples were a mixture of blood from different pigs, whereby each sample came from different

mixtures. The experiments of blood with heparin started within four hours after collection.

III. RESULTS

Fig. 2 and 3 show the complex relative permittivity

$$\epsilon(\omega, \vartheta) = \epsilon'(\omega, \vartheta) - i\epsilon''(\omega, \vartheta) \quad (1)$$

and the effective conductivity

$$\sigma(\omega, \vartheta) = \omega\epsilon_0\epsilon''(\omega, \vartheta) \quad (2)$$

where the real part ϵ' represents the relative permittivity, the imaginary part ϵ'' the relative dielectric loss, ϵ_0 the permittivity of free space, $\omega = 2\pi f$ the angular frequency and ϑ the temperature.

Fig. 2(a) and (c) show the mean value of the relative permittivity and effective conductivity of fresh blood without heparin as a function of frequency at different temperatures. The relative permittivity decreases with increasing temperature due to the high water content of blood. The maximum temperature dependent permittivity change of $\Delta\epsilon' \approx 4$ occurs

Fig. 3: Relative permittivity and conductivity of porcine and human blood at $f = 1.76$ GHz and $f = 3.0$ GHz as a function of temperature. \circ show the data of three different blood samples without heparin. Dashed blue lines show linear fits to the mean relative permittivity and the mean effective conductivity of this study. \triangle show the data presented by Cook [12]. Dashed red lines illustrate the linear fit to data reported by Cook.

in the frequency range between $1 \text{ GHz} < f < 2.5 \text{ GHz}$. At higher frequencies the temperature dependence falls down to $\Delta\epsilon' \approx 1$ at $f = 7 \text{ GHz}$. The effective conductivity shows a point of intersection at 3°C where the conductivity does not change with temperature. Below this point, conductivity rises with increasing temperature. This dependency reverses for frequencies above the point of intersection. Fig. 2(b) and (d) show the mean value of the relative permittivity and effective conductivity of fresh blood mixtures with heparin as a function of frequency at different temperatures. The curves show nearly no differences compared to the fresh blood sample without heparin.

Fig. 3 compares the relative permittivity and effective conductivity at two single frequencies ($f = 1.76$ GHz and $f = 3.0$ GHz) as a function of temperature with the data of human blood presented by Cook [12]. We calculated linear fits to the data of our study as well as to the data of Cook. The values of the relative permittivity reported by Cook are lower compared with the data of our study, whereby the linear

decrease is compatible with our measurements. The results obtained on the effective conductivity differ more significantly. If we consider the data reported by Cook it seems that there is an intersection point at $f \approx 1.8 \text{ GHz}$, because at this frequency there is no change in conductivity, whereby at the higher frequency $f = 3.0 \text{ GHz}$ the conductivity shows a decreasing trend with increasing temperature. The effective conductivity obtained in this study shows a similar trend as it decreases with increasing temperature above the intersection point ($f > 3.0 \text{ GHz}$) as depicted in Fig. 2(c) and (d). A further comparative parameter are the temperature coefficients:

$$\frac{\Delta\epsilon'}{\epsilon'} \text{ in } (\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}) \text{ and } \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\sigma} \text{ in } (\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}) \quad (3)$$

which describe the changes of the dielectric properties divided by a reference value. We chose these values corresponding to the dielectric properties at 25°C . Jaspard investigated the temperature coefficients for human and animal blood and summarized $-0.3\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ for the relative permittivity and

TABLE I: Temperature coefficients at 1 GHz.

	$\Delta\varepsilon'/\varepsilon'$	$\Delta\sigma'/\sigma$
Jaspard [9]	$-0.3\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$1.0\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
This study	$-0.31\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$1.58\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$

$1\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ for the effective conductivity at 1 GHz. Table I shows the temperature coefficients based on our data in comparison with the coefficients presented by Jaspard [9]. The temperature coefficients of the relative permittivity are identical for both studies. The temperature coefficient of the effective conductivity shows a higher value in our study compared with Jaspard.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this contribution we measured temperature dependent dielectric properties of porcine blood with and without heparin in the temperature range between 30°C and 50°C from 0.5 GHz to 7 GHz. The results show that heparin has no influence on the temperature dependent dielectric properties of blood. To compare the results of our study with the data known from literature, we calculated linear fits, which show a good agreement for the relative permittivity at single frequencies in the considered temperature range, but the linear approximation of the conductivity depending on the temperature might be not sufficient for a wide temperature range (especially at the cross-over point near 3 GHz), which is also postulated by Lazebnik [8].

In addition to the temperature dependent measurements of the relative permittivity and effective conductivity of blood, further studies of tissues (e. g. muscle, liver, fat) are planned in order to estimate temperature changes within phantom experiments based on UWB radar measurements.

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